

STATISTICAL AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF WEAR TOOL GEOMETRY IN DRILLING CFRP

N. Feito¹, A. Sánchez-Muñoz¹, J. López-Puente², H. Miguelez¹

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Avda de la Universidad 30, 28911, Leganés (Madrid), Spain
Email: mhmiguelez@ing.uc3m.es, web page: <http://www.uc3m.es>

²Department of Continuum Media and Structural Analysis, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Avda de la Universidad 30, 28911, Leganés (Madrid), Spain
Email: jlpuente@ing.uc3m.es, web page: <http://www.uc3m.es>

Keywords: Tool wear, CFRP, Modelling, Drilling, Finite elements

ABSTRACT

Although composite components are manufactured close to the final shape, they usually require machining operations in order to achieve dimensional tolerances and assembly specifications. This is the case of Carbon Fiber Reinforce Polymers usually used in aerospace industry due to its excellent mechanical properties. In this industry, drilling operations are required before mechanical joining of the components to manufacture huge lightweight structures. The life in service of the components normally is affected by delamination damage and the reduction of the extension of this damage is one of the main goals in the composites field. An experimental and statistical analysis has been carried out in woven CFRPs drilling to study the influence of the geometry in delamination. Three different point angles and two wear levels were tested: fresh tool and honed edge tool. The results showed increasing feed forces when increasing the point angle and the wear. On the other hand, delamination damage shows dependency mainly with wear. In this case, the influence of the feed rate is more relevant than point angle. Finally a numerical model for both geometries was developed and validated to predict thrust force and delamination.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymers (CFRPs) materials present an excellent combination of fatigue and corrosion resistance, light weight and high specific stiffness and strength, what make them appropriate for high responsibility applications [1]. Among different type of such materials, woven composites are significant in the family of CFRPs. Their higher strength-to weight ratio, higher fracture toughness and excellent corrosion resistance properties compared to unidirectional composites, have proven it to be appealing as first option for material solution.

Today, drilling is still a common manufacturing process to get joining composites using mechanical joints like screws, rivets and bolts [2]. To achieve required dimensional tolerances, the quality must be ensured during the drilling operation. Between all damages that can be found during drilling, delamination has been recognized as the most important of all of them by many authors [3]. This phenomenon is related with two main variables: the cutting parameters and the tool geometry.

By one side, earlier studies about the influence of cuttings parameters on delamination damage in drilling woven CFRP materials showed that the cutting speed would be the least influential parameter [4]. For feed force also is showed a slight influence. However, it has been proved that the feed rate is much more influential on both, damage generation (delamination) and thrust force during drilling operations [5, 6].

On the other side, the main studies related with the geometry of the drill bit and its influence on delamination proved that whereas the drilling torque remains almost constant, the thrust force increase with the point angle. Opposite to this, the quality at the entrance of the hole was better than at the exit when high point angles are used [4]. The same effect has been observed at the entry of the hole in cross-ply composite materials with twist drill bits [7]. Another study proved that for double-point angle drill bit the hole diameter tolerance was more critical at elevated feed rates than the exit delamination criterion [8].

Due to the abrasive character of the fibers, the initial design of the drill bit is modified when the number of machining cycles increases. The evolution of wear is an influencing factor in the surface integrity, especially at the exit at the hole. For tests at high speeds of drilling (10,000–15,000 rpm), the abrasive wear has been found to be more significant than chipping on the primary cutting edge [9]. Under normal cutting conditions, also abrasion was found as first wear mechanism [10]. Adhesion of the matrix could be considered in second place, with much lower effect [10]. These effects occur with different intensity depending on the cutting speed and the feed rate. In addition, exit delamination of the drill increases with the number of drill holes, due to wear. It has been proved also that the wear of uncoated and coated carbide tools was strongly related with contact length and axial force applied to the cutting edge [5, 11].

The only one effect analysed due to abrasion, was the Cutting Edge Rounding (CER) studied in [12] during drilling of woven CFRP materials. It was concluded that both, delamination and cutting forces, presented a positive correlation with the CER. The influence of this phenomenon in orthogonal cutting has been studied previously by the authors [13] reaching similar conclusions.

Despite to all the studies relates with drilling to improve delamination damage, limited 'statistical' studies can be found in the literature. The study [6] showed that the cutting speed has less influence on the peel-up, when compared to the effect of feed rate. However on push-out, contribution percentages of both of these cutting parameters were nearly the same under different tool geometries. For small drills, [5] an ANOVA analysis was carried out with six input parameters. Results put in relief that for entry delamination the drill type was the only significant parameter, with no influence from cutting parameters. On the other hand, the point angle and feed rate were significant on thrust force, and the cutting speed and feed rate were influential on torque.

Finite element modelling of drilling of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) composites is an interesting tool for damage prediction. The recent models developed for unidirectional laminates reproduced successfully the drill penetration in the workpiece, material failure and elements erosion [14, 15]. A recent paper developed by authors has compared this kind of models with a simplified model [16].

This paper presents an experimental analysis about the effect of drill point angle and wear level on hole quality. Thrust force and delamination have been evaluated. Also the effect of cutting parameters (cutting speed and feed rate) were studied and statically analysed for a better understanding about the influence of each one on the output parameters. Finally a new FEM model for CFRP materials has been developed for new and honed edge tools and it has been validated in terms of thrust force and maximum delamination.

2 EXPERIMENTAL WORK

2.1 Drill Bits and Workpiece Material

The experimental work was carried out with two different tools, related with different wear evolution stages: a twisted fresh drill bit and a twisted honed edge drill bit. The second one is related to chipping wear and has a total length equal to 0.05 mm (see Fig.1). Both tools had a 6 mm diameter and were uncoated. Each drill was tested for three values of point angle 90°, 118° and 140°,

recommended for CFRP drilling by GUHRING Manufacturer Company. The worn geometry was artificially generated using grinding.

Figure 1: Edge geometry for Fresh tool (A) and Honed Edge Tool (B).

The material selected was woven CFRP, based on AS-4 carbon fibre and 8552 epoxy matrix manufactured by Hexcel Composites. Each coupon is composed by 10 plies with a total thickness of 2.2 mm. The mechanical properties of this material are presented in Table 1.

ρ	$E_1=E_2$	E_3	ν_{12}	Resin content
1570 Kg/m ³	68 GPa	10 GPa	0.31	55.29%
$X_t = Y_t$	$X_c = Y_c$	S_t	$\epsilon_1=\epsilon_2$	ϵ_3
795 MPa	860 MPa	98 MPa	0.025	0.05

Table 1: Mechanical properties of carbon-epoxy woven laminate.

2.2 Machining Test

The cutting tests were carried out on a B500 KONDIA machining center. A rotating cutting force dynamometer (Kistler 9123C) was used for measure the thrust force in feed direction as well as the drive moment on the rotating tool. The drilling experiments were conducted without coolant and the cutting parameters are shown in Table 2.

Parameter	Values		
f [mm/rev]	0.05	0.1	0.15
V [m/min]	25	50	100

Table 2: Selected cutting parameters for feed rate (f) and cutting speed (V).

The delamination factor (F_D) was quantified as the ratio between the maximum diameter of delaminated area, measure on images obtained with a stereo microscope (Optika SZR), and the nominal diameter (Eq. (1)).

$$F_D = D_{max} / D_{nom} \quad (1)$$

3 NUMERICAL MODELL

A 3D model able to reproduce the complete drill process for woven CFRP materials has been implemented. The drill was assumed to be rigid, with diameter equal to 6 mm and the tip angle equal to 118°. Two geometries have been modelled, one for fresh drill and the other one for honed edge tool. The rotatory and the feed movements of the drill were imposed in Z direction over the drill (Fig. 2). The model also includes geometrical non-linearity and large deformations options. Displacement was not allowed in the contour of the piece and in Z direction in the base of the workpiece except inside a circumference with diameter 10 mm where it is free.

Figure 2: Scheme of the model.

3.1 Workpiece modelling

The carbon/epoxy woven laminate has been modeled as an orthotropic elastic material until failure. To model material failure, intra-laminar and inter-laminar damage mechanisms are defined. The first one has been implemented by means of a user subroutine in ABAQUS. This model considers two different types of damage (fiber failure and crushing matrix failure) and defines different damage variables d (stress dependent) that vary from 0 (no damage) to 1 (fully broken).

Fiber Failure	Plane Direction 1	$d_{f1} = \begin{cases} \frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_t} & \text{if } \sigma_{11} > 0 \\ \frac{ \sigma_{11} }{X_c} & \text{if } \sigma_{11} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$
	Plane Direction 2	$d_{f2} = \begin{cases} \frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_t} & \text{if } \sigma_{22} > 0 \\ \frac{ \sigma_{22} }{Y_c} & \text{if } \sigma_{22} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$
Crushing Matrix Failure	Plane Direction	$d_{m12} = \left \frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}} \right \quad (4)$
	Through-Thickness Direction	$d_{m3} = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{Z_c} \right)^2 + \frac{Z_c \cdot \sigma_{33}}{4S_{13}S_{23}} + \left \frac{\sigma_{33}}{Z_c} \right + \max \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{S_{13}} \right)^2, \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{S_{23}} \right)^2 \right] \quad (5)$

Table 3: Equations used to describe the failure models implemented in the model.

When d equals one, the material loses its strength and hence some of the stress components are set to zero. Table 3 presents all the equations which describe the failure models implemented where σ_{ij} are components of the stress tensor, X_t and X_c are the strengths of the composite laminate in tension and compression for the first direction, Y_t and Y_c are the strengths in tension and compression for the

second direction, S_{12} , S_{13} and S_{23} are the shear strengths in the three different planes and finally Z_c is the strength in the through-thickness direction under compression. The Eq. (5) applies only when $\sigma_{33} < 0$. This implementation of different failure mechanisms has been used in previous works of the authors [17, 18].

The second one has been taken into account using cohesive elements. These elements are based on a traction-separation law. To define the law it is necessary to specify the linear elastic behavior by means of the correspondent stiffness (K_{nn} , K_{ss} and K_{tt}), the initiation of the damage by means of the interface resistance (t_n , t_s and t_t) and the damage evolution by means of the critical released rate energies (G_n^C ; G_s^C and G_t^C).

In this case, for the damage initiation a quadratic nominal stress criterion has been implemented, similar to Eq. (6), where t_n , t_s and t_t are the strengths of the cohesive interface in the normal and in the two shear directions respectively. This last equation is applied if one of conditions on Eq. (7) is reached, where Z_t is the laminate strength under tension in the through thickness direction

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{t_n}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{t_s}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{t_t}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_{33} \geq Z_t \text{ or } \sqrt{\sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2} \geq S_{23} \quad (7)$$

For the case of the damage evolution law, a potential law type based on energies as Eq. (8) has been chosen where G_n , G_s and G_t are the released rates energies in the three directions, G_n^C ; G_s^C and G_t^C are the critical values of the released rates energies, and α a parameter of the model ($\alpha = 1$ for this case). All the values for these constants are showed in Table 4.

$$\left(\frac{G_n}{G_n^C}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_s}{G_s^C}\right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_t}{G_t^C}\right)^\alpha \geq 1 \quad (8)$$

K_{nn}	K_{ss}	K_{tt}	t_n	t_s	t_t	G_n	G_s	G_t
2	1.5	1.5	11	45	45	0.6	1.8	1.8
GPa/mm	GPa/mm	GPa/mm	MPa	MPa	MPa	J/m ²	J/m ²	J/m ²

Table 4: Properties of the cohesive elements.

3.2 Finite Element Mesh

To minimize the dependence of the results with mesh orientation in the ply, wedge solid elements C3D6R were used in the zone close to the drill entrance. For these elements a size minimum of 0.2 mm was imposed. Far from to the drill entrance zone hexagonal elements C3D8R with 8 nodes and reduced integration were used, with minimum element size around 1mm. One element is imposed along the thickness.

The cohesive plies were modelled with small thickness (50 microns) in order to improve numerical behavior when elevated deformations are reached during calculation. Meshing strategy in the plane 1-2 was the same as that used in the ply, with one element along the thickness (direction 3).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Thrust force

The maximum thrust force obtained during drilling tests is presented in Fig. 3. Fresh tools showed a low influence of the point angle in comparison with worn tool. For all angles the increment of feed rate lead to increment the thrust force (values of thrust force between 50 and 150 N for all cases). However, no significant effects were observed with the variation of the cutting speed.

In the case of honing tools, the increment of point angle presented a clear growing tendency: around 50% regardless of the value of cutting speed tested. On the other hand, the increase of the feed per revolution from 0.05 mm/rev to 0.15 mm/rev showed higher influence when the point angle grows up. Raising the feed with same point angle led to an increment around 85% in thrust force. It is clear that the wear strongly increases the effect of the point angle and feed rate on thrust force.

Figure 3: Variation of Thrust Force for fresh tool (A) and honed edge tool (B) for cutting speed equal 100 m/min.

For new tool has been observed decreasing values of the torque when the point angle is increased from 90° to 118° and slight increment when it changes from 118° to 140°. For worn tool the trend is the opposite and maximum values of the torque are observed for the point angle 118°.

4.2 Delamination

During the study was observed that exit delamination is for all cases higher than the found for entrance delamination. The results showed in Fig. 4 are only concerning the push-out. For fresh tool, the same effect observed previously in thrust force was reproduced for delamination; the damage decreased slightly for 118° point angle and increased for 140°. The minimum and maximum values were reached for the lowest and highest feed rate respectively (0.05 mm/rev and 0.15 mm/rev).

Figure 4: Variation of delamination for fresh tool (A) and honed edge tool (B).

On the other hand, honed edge tool increased the damage for high point angle. This fact is related to the increment of the thrust force due to wear progression. In comparison with fresh tool, delamination presented higher values for honed drill bit reaching a factor equal 1.6 while the maximum values for fresh drill are equal 1.35.

With the increase of the wear, this difference between in and out delamination was higher. This is due to when the edge starts to wear the geometry is going flattering and the peeling force through the

slope of the drill decreases. This fact elevates the thrust force but decreases the peel force, what results into reduces the peel-up and increases the push-out mechanisms.

4.3 ANOVA study

Table 5 shows the results obtained from the ANOVA analysis on the thrust force response. It can be observed that only two of the three parameters are directly related to the thrust force (point angle and feed rate) independently of the tool geometry (P-value < 0.05). The relative percentage contributions of these factors, however, change when the wear level increases on the drill bit; for the new tool the feed rate has the main influence (57.46%). On contrary, honed edge tool shows comparable contributions of the two factors.

	Factor	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean Square	F-Value	P-value	Contribution of SS_{Mean}	Significance
New Tool	Point angle (A)	2987.512	2	1493.756	141.2005	5.76E-07	37.23%	Very High
	Cutting speed (B)	52.82743	2	26.41372	2.496812	0.143694	0.66%	Insignificant
	Feed rate (C)	4610.603	2	2305.301	217.9135	1.06E-07	57.46%	Very High
	AB	136.0129	4	34.00323	3.214228	0.075016	0.85%	Insignificant
	AC	126.1262	4	31.53156	2.980588	0.088243	0.79%	Insignificant
	BC	441.957	4	110.4892	10.44423	0.002907	2.75%	Very Low
	Residual	84.6318	8	10.57898	-	-	0.26%	-
	Total	8439.67	26	-	-	-	100%	-
Honed Edge Tool	Point angle (A)	100141.9	2	50070.96	128.6085	8.28E-07	47.41%	Very High
	Cutting Speed (B)	1630.257	2	815.1283	2.093678	0.185662	0.77%	Insignificant
	Feed rate (C)	100965.8	2	50482.9	129.6666	8.02E-07	47.80%	Very High
	AB	4616.701	4	1154.175	2.964528	0.089253	1.09%	Insignificant
	AC	8287.652	4	2071.913	5.321761	0.021754	1.96%	Very Low
	BC	2486.189	4	621.5472	1.59646	0.265445	0.59%	Insignificant
	Residual	3114.628	8	389.3284	-	-	0.37%	-
	Total	221243.2	26	-	-	-	100%	-

Table 5: ANOVA analysis for thrust force.

Cutting speed did not show a statistically significant influence on the thrust force for any tool case (p -value > 0.05). However, based on Table 5, it has a slight influence in combination with other significant main parameters (BC interaction factor). The contribution of this interaction is quite low for the case of new tool (2.75%), which means that practically it is not as important as the point angle. For worn tool, the interaction factor AC is slightly significant, but its percentage contribution is still low compared to the main factors. The rest of the interactions for each case are not significant and their contribution is always lower than 1%.

The same study was carried out for delamination (Table 6). In this case, for fresh tool the three drilling parameters are significant being the point angle the most influential of all of them (~40% contribution). It is also interesting that the cutting speed is influential (with a low contribution) on the delamination, in contrast to results observed in Table 5.

For the case of honed edge tool, the point angle and feed rate becomes both significant and not the cutting speed. In contrast of new tool, the contribution of feed rate is higher than point angle. Finally, it is evident from Table 6 that delamination is more sensitive to the wear and a more complex response to minimize (the effect of AB interaction which is not negligible in these cases). Notice also that for both cases the other two interactions (AC and BC) are insignificant and the influence is lower than 5.7% for the most unfavorable case.

	Factor	Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom	Mean Square	F-Value	P-Value	Contribution of SS_{Mean}	Significance
New Tool	Point angle (A)	0.058	2	0.029	23.91	0.0004	41.82%	Very High
	Cutting speed (B)	0.013	2	6.27E-03	5.21	0.0356	9.04%	Very Low
	Feed rate (C)	0.025	2	0.012	10.29	0.0061	17.31%	Very High
	AB	0.062	4	0.015	12.82	0.0015	21.63%	Very High
	AC	7.79E-03	4	1.95E-03	1.62	0.2603	2.81%	Insignificant
	BC	0.016	4	3.92E-03	3.26	0.0729	5.65%	Insignificant
	Residual	9.63E-03	8	1.20E-03	-	-	1.74%	-
	Total	0.19	26	-	-	-	100%	-
Honed Edge Tool	Point angle (A)	0.147998	2	0.073999	11.95297	0.003953	34.31%	Very High
	Cutting Speed (B)	0.016753	2	0.008376	1.353034	0.311774	3.88%	Insignificant
	Feed rate (C)	0.202589	2	0.101295	16.36206	0.001489	46.97%	Very High
	AB	0.090622	4	0.022655	3.659526	0.045933	10.50%	Low
	AC	0.004073	4	0.001018	0.164477	0.950542	0.47%	Insignificant
	BC	0.00859	4	0.002148	0.346889	0.839234	1.00%	Insignificant
	Residual	0.049527	8	0.006191	-	-	2.87%	-
	Total	0.520152	26	-	-	-	100%	-

Table 6: ANOVA analysis for delamination.

4.4 Model Validation

The complete developed model was validated through the comparison with experimental results provided for cutting speed equal 100 m/min and 118° point angle. The model was validated in terms of thrust force and maximum delamination. Fig. 5 and 6 show reasonable accuracy when predicting these parameters.

Figure 5: Comparison between experimental and estimated thrust force and delamination for new and honed tools.

The thrust force prediction for fresh tool was better than honed tool. In all cases prediction error was not higher than 5%. On the other hand delamination prediction was also higher in the model than in experimental with a maximum deviation of 4.5%. This model is therefore conservative in predicting delamination. Thus the model could be used as prediction tool of surface integrity.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results acquired, the major conclusions can be drawn in this study:

With the experimental study, it was proved that point angle has no strong influence when drilling with fresh tool. However, the increment of feed leads to increasing thrust force for all values of point angle in both geometries. In general, the maximum delamination factor was below 1.6. The trend of delamination factor is to increase with the point angle due to the enhancement of thrust force. As consequence of this, the worn geometry causes the highest delamination working with high cutting parameters.

Statically analysis showed that feed rate and point angle are the factors with highest influence on the thrust force. When the tool is new, the point angle is the most influent parameter. When the tool geometry changes due to wear, the feed rate becomes more important. On the other hand, cutting speed does not present relevant influence on the thrust force. Concerning delamination, it was concluded that point angle has a strong influence. In contrast with thrust force, cutting speed is significant but its influence is generally low compared to other cutting parameters. For honed edge tool feed rate is the most influence input related with delamination damage.

Finally a new FE model able to predict the drilling thrust force with reasonable accuracy for woven materials has been validated. The model was successfully tested with fresh and honed edge drill bits. Due to the maximum delamination predicted is slightly over-estimated, it can be said that the model present a conservative prediction of damage delamination.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the financial support for this work to the Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness of Spain under the project DPI2011-25999 and FPI subprogram with the reference BES-2012-055162.

REFERENCES

- [1] X. Huang, Fabrication and Properties of Carbon Fibers, *Materials*, **2**, 2009, pp. 2369-2403
- [2] C. Santiuste, E. Barbero, M.H. Miguélez, Computational analysis of temperature effect in composite bolted joints for aeronautical applications, *J. Reinf. Plast. Compos*, **30**, 2011, pp. 3-11
- [3] D. Liu, Y.J. Tang, W.L. Cong, A review of mechanical drilling for composite laminates, *Compos. Struct.*, **94**, 2012, pp. 1265-1279
- [4] U. Heisel, T. Pfeifroth, Influence of Point Angle on Drill Hole Quality and Machining Forces when Drilling CFRP, *5th CIRP Conference on High Performance Cutting 2012*, Procedia CIRP 1, 2012, pp. 471-476
- [5] I.S. Shyha, D.K. Aspinwall, S.L. Soo, S. Bradley, Drill geometry and operating effects when cutting small diameter holes in CFRP, *Int. J. Mach. Tools Manuf.* **49**, 2009, pp. 1008-1014
- [6] J.P. Davim, P. Reis, Drilling carbon fiber plastics manufactures by autoclave – experimental and statistical study, *Materials & design*, **24**, 2003, pp. 315-324
- [7] P. Durão, J.S. Gonçalves, R.S. Tavares, C. de Albuquerque, A. Aguiar, A. Torres, Drilling tool geometry evaluation for reinforced composite laminates, *Compos. Struct.* **92**, 2010, pp.1545-1550

- [8] Y. Karpát, B. Deger, O. Bahtiyar, Drilling thick fabric woven CFRP laminates with double point angle drills, *J. Mater. Process. Technol.*, **212**, 2012, pp. 2117-2127
- [9] S. Rawat, H. Attia, Wear mechanisms and tool life management of WC–Co drills during dry high speed drilling of woven carbon fibre composites, *Wear*, **267**, 2009, pp. 1022-1030
- [10] P. Mayuet, A. Gallo, A. Portal, P. Arroyo, M. Alvarez, M. Marcos, Damaged Area based Study of the Break-IN and Break-OUT defects in the Dry Drilling of Carbon fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP). *The Manufacturing Engineering Society International Conference, MESIC 2013 Procedia Engineering* 63, 2013, pp. 743-751
- [11] D. Iliescu, D. Gehin, M.E. Gutierrez, F. Girot, Modeling and tool wear in drilling of CFRP, *Int. J. Mach. Tools Manuf.*, **50**, 2010, pp. 204-213
- [12] A. Faraz, D. Biermann, K. Weinert, Cutting edge rounding: An innovative tool wear criterion in drilling CFRP composite laminates, *Int. J. Mach. Tools Manuf.*, **49**, 2009, pp. 1185-1196.
- [13] X. Soldani, C. Santiuste, A. Muñoz-Sánchez, M.H. Miguélez, Influence of tool geometry and numerical parameters when modeling orthogonal cutting of LFRP composites, *Compos. Part A*, **42**, 2011, 1205-1216
- [14] VA. Phadnis, F. Makhdam, A. Roy, VV. Silberschmidt, Drilling in carbon/epoxy composites: experimental investigations and finite element implementation, *Compos A Appl Sci Manuf*, **47**, 2013, pp. 41-51
- [15] O. Isbilir, E. Ghassemieh, Numerical investigation of the effects of drill geometry on drilling induced delamination of carbon fiber reinforced composites, *Compos Struct.*, **105**, 2013 pp.126-33, 2013.
- [16] N. Feito, J. López-Puente, C. Santiuste, M.H. Miguélez, Numerical prediction of delamination in CFRP drilling, *Composite Structures*, **108**, 2014, pp. 677-683.
- [17] J. López-Puente, R. Zaera, C. Navarro, Experimental and numerical analysis of normal and oblique ballistic impacts on thin carbon/epoxy woven laminates, *Compos. Part A*, **39**, 2008, 374-387
- [18] D. Varas, J.A. Artero-Guerrero, J. Pernas-Sánchez, J. López-Puente, Analysis of high velocity impacts of steel cylinders on thin carbon/epoxy woven laminates, *Composite Structures*, **95**, 2013, pp. 623–629